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Manifesto Gender Analysis

Codebook

Version 1.0

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1. Introduction

This document consists in the codebook of the manifesto analysis developed by the Saarland University team (Working package 4, hereinafter WP4) for the EU Horizon UNTWIST project. The aim of the working package is to gauge how political parties represent gender-related issues in their political manifestos by collecting all the manifestos issued by political parties ahead of national (general) and European Parliament (EP) elections in six European countries (Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Spain, Switzerland, and United Kingdom) between 2003 and 2021. This document contains information on the coding procedure and the coding categories and dimensions for the content analysis of party manifestos.

1.1 The analysis of party manifestos

The comparative analysis of party manifestos – i.e., election programs of political parties – aims at measuring issue salience and policy positions of political parties across countries using a common framework.

Programmatic statements are central features of political parties. They put political ideas and goals of parties on record. Although only few voters actually read party documents, mass media commonly spread their contents and usually represent the core of different party documents issued in many countries for this sort of research. Therefore, the advantages of using party manifestos in order to identify political goals of parties are manifold:

- Manifestos cover a wide range of themes, problems, and political positions and, therefore, contain a “set of key central statements.”

- They are authoritative statements of party policies because party conventions usually ratify them.
- They comprise statements that represent the whole party, not just individual party members or one of its factions.
- Political parties usually release them before elections. This enables studies of changes in issue emphases and policy positions in a diachronic perspective.

All documents collected by the UNTWIST Project are party manifestos¹ released before a national election or an election to the European Parliament between 2004 and 2021.

2. Coding procedure

The coding procedure includes all the necessary steps for completing the gender analysis of party manifestos. The procedure for each manifesto can be broken down in two main tasks: the [classification of quasi-sentences](#), and the [completion of a survey](#). The following three sections (from 2.1 to 2.3) deal with the former, whereas the last one (2.4) deals with the latter.

¹ The political parties themselves are not necessarily the only source of information when it comes to accessing party manifestos. Research and educational institutes often times provide these pieces of information. Newspapers, magazines, or books occasionally serve as transmitters as well. In some countries, parties do not distribute manifestos. Hence, party manifestos represent an *ideal type* of documents to search for, which usually can be found but sometimes not. In the latter cases, alternative documents are employed, such as election pledges of parties released in newspapers or reports by official spokespersons of a party on policy positions and intentions. Yet, these kinds of documents are to represent information sources of last resort only.

2.1 Quasi-sentences classification

Before starting the annotation and classification of the quasi-sentences the coder should remember some *basic rules*. Which have been proven to be useful – if not *crucial* – for a robust classification of quasi-sentences, and party manifesto analysis in general.

First, the coder should get familiar with the coding categories provided in Section 3. This would allow the coder to proceed faster and more confidently in the classification tasks.

Second, the coder should be careful in selecting residual categories during the annotation process. Among the options, the coder should pay attention to: (i) use the “does not apply” category – i.e., category 0 – in Step 1; (ii) apply the domain-specific “other” categories in Step 2; and (iii) select the “neutral” category when selecting the connotation of a statement in Step 4.

Finally, for avoiding misclassification in any of the previous steps (and the remaining ones), the coder should also evaluate the sentences or the paragraph surrounding a quasi-sentence, or the title of the section in which it appears.

2.1.1 Unitisation

The coding units of the MGA are quasi-sentences and the whole manifestos. While the latter unit of measure can be grasped straightforwardly and mostly pertains to the completion of the expert survey (see Section 2.4), the former one is not, and deserves a few words for being defined.

A quasi-sentence is an argument, and the latter constitutes what this project is primarily interested in. An argument is a verbal expression of a political idea or issue. In its simplest form, a sentence is the basic unit of meaning. Punctuation thus offers a guideline for identifying arguments. A sentence always has a subject and a verb, and oftentimes objects, attributes and adjectives.

Example (1) *'We make a stand for gender equality.'*
'We support more rights for LGBTQI+ people.'

These two sentences obviously contain two readily identifiable and distinguishable arguments. Language, however, often adopts higher levels of complexity. It is also subject to linguistic, rhetorical, and purposive phrasing how to express one and the same political ideas.

Example (2) *'We make a stand for gender equality and support more rights for LGBTQI+ people.'*

Example (2) combines the two statements in example (1) in one sentence. Nonetheless, the project still treats them as two distinct arguments. Whenever changes in terms of argumentation occur within a sentence, a coder is to dissect the latter into quasi-sentences. Iterative nouns and/or verbs often indicate that a given sentence contains more than one argument. Hence, they can also be used as markers of quasi-sentences in longer sentences which are likely to contain several distinct arguments. Accordingly, each quasi-sentence is to contain only one single political idea

or issue. It is complete at the end of that distinct argument. Full stops always set an end of an argument, whereas other forms of punctuation often but not necessarily do so.

2.1.2 Classification

After splitting the manifesto in quasi-sentences, the coder should then move to the following task, namely the classification of these sentences according to the coding scheme presented below in the text (see Sections 2.2 and 2.3). In order to properly classify the quasi-sentences, each coder should follow a set of 7 steps (see also Figure 1):

- Step 0) Unitize the paragraph;
- Step 1) Decide whether (score = 1) the quasi-sentence refers to gender-related issues (i.e., whether the quasi-sentence can be assigned to any of the predefined domains and categories) and then move to the following step, or not (score = 0);
- Step 2) If a quasi-sentence refers to a gender-related goal, issue or policy (Step 1, score = 1), define (2.1) the domain and (2.2) the coding category to be applied to the quasi-sentence;
- Step 3) Decide whether a quasi-sentence refers to a specific recipient or group in terms of (3.1 and 3.2) gender and/or (3.3) sexual orientation, and move to Step 4. If not, jump to Step 5 (see scores below);
- Step 4) Evaluate the intersectionality of the statement in Step 3;

Step 5) Define whether the quasi-sentence has a negative (score = 1), neutral (score = 2), or positive (score = 3) connotation;²

Step 6) Decide whether the quasi-sentence refers to a goal (score = 1), an issue (score = 2), or a policy (score = 3). If the statement refers to a policy (3), the coder should perform Step 7, otherwise move to the following quasi-sentence;

Step 7) Decide whether the policy identified in Step 6 is (1) a relief or resource-based measure, (2) a regulation, (3) another kind of measure, or (0) an undefined one.

In short, all the steps after unitisation are *conditional* on Step 1. If a category applies (Step 1, score = 1) then the remaining steps are performed, with (i) Step 4 conditional on Step 3, and (ii) Step 7 conditional on Step 6.

Here is an example on how to apply the coding scheme:

Example (3) ‘[We stand for gender equality in the welfare system.] [In the next legislature we will support an extension of parental leave for both parents], [and increase the provision of public childcare services].’

These two natural sentences include 3 quasi-sentences (EX. 3.1, EX 3.2, EX. 3.3), delimited by the square brackets, that should be coded as it follows:

² The *specific* meaning of these connotations might vary across coding categories. Therefore, check the provided examples in each category before annotating the connotation.

Q.S.	DOMAIN	CATE GORY	RECIP. GENDER	RECIP. GENDER (CIS-TRANS)	RECIP. SEXUALITY	INTER SECTION	N.N.P.	G.I.P.	POLICY
EX. 3,1	2	6	0	0	0	0	3	1	0
EX. 3,2	2	1	0	0	0	0	3	3	4
EX. 3,2	2	2	0	0	0	0	3	3	4

Legenda: Q.S. = quasi-sentence. Recip. = Recipient; N.N.P. = Negative, neutral, or positive. G.I.P. = Goal, issue, or policy.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the coding steps

2.2 Coding categories: goals, issues, and policies

The current coding scheme is composed of 5 domains and 25 coding categories.

Domain 1: Labour Market

1.1 Salary/Pay gap

Positive: Includes statements concerning the reduction of the gap as a goal, issue to be addressed, or policies aiming at reducing it. This might include statements concerning pension gaps as a consequence of the salary gap.

Negative: Includes statements justifying, minimising, or denying the gap, policies proposals that might increase (directly or indirectly) the gap. This might include statements concerning pension gaps as a consequence of the salary gap.

Neutral: Undefined connotation of the gap.

1.2 Division of labour

Positive: Statements concerning increasing gender equality in labour division.

Negative: Statements advocating or justifying inequalities concerning division of labour.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

1.3 Labour rights and discrimination

Positive: Includes statements in favour of gender equality in terms of labour rights and against gender-based discrimination in the workplace.

Negative: Includes advocating or justifying gender-based inequalities within the workplace or in the labour market, or budget cuts for policies in favour of gender equality in terms of rights.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

Check against 4.1: *This category captures statements which refer only to labour-related rights and discrimination.*

1.4 Other

Positive: Other statements in favour of gender equality in the labour market.

Negative: Other statements against gender equality or justifying inequalities in the labour market.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

NB: *This category captures only statements referring to labour-related goals, issues, or policies which are not included in the previous categories.*

Domain 2: Welfare and family

2.1 Parental leave

Positive: Includes statements in favour of equal opportunities for parents to obtain parental leave.

Negative: Includes statements advocating or justifying gender inequalities, or promoting policies which foster inequalities, or against gender-equal policies concerning parental leaves.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

NB: *Promotion of parental leave policies, or budget cuts, are not positive or negative per se. Coders must evaluate whether these diminish or aggravate existing inequalities.*

2.2 Childcare and housework

Positive: Includes statements supporting shared responsibilities within the household, or policies alleviating or compensating parents' childcare and housework. Negative mentions of inequalities within the household.

Negative: Includes statements advocating or justifying inequalities within the household (e.g., women should be

mostly responsible for these activities). Promotion of policies or policy changes increasing inequalities.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

2.3 Other care work

Positive: Includes statements supporting shared responsibilities within the household. Negative mentions of inequalities within the household. In favour of policies alleviating or compensating nursing, elder care, and other forms of care work.

Negative: Includes statements advocating or justifying inequalities within the household (e.g., women should be mostly responsible for these activities). Promotion of policies or policy changes increasing inequalities.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

2.4 Healthcare

Positive: Includes statements supporting access to healthcare or equal treatment specifically for (cis or trans) women, non-binary, queer, or other gender identities.

Negative: Includes statements against or curtailing access to healthcare or equal treatment specifically for (cis or trans) women, non-binary, queer, or other gender identities.

Neutral: Undefined connotation

Check against 4.1: Does not include reproductive rights.

2.5 Education

Positive: statements in favour of equality of opportunity and access to education; equal rights in education; non-discrimination in education; support for non-traditional vocations for women; raising awareness and combating gender stereotypes through education.

Negative: statements in favour of inequalities or justifying or minimising said inequalities in education. Promotion of gender

inequalities, gender stereotypes, educational discrimination, or traditional vocation for women.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

2.6 Other

Positive: Includes other statements in favour of gender equality in the welfare system.

Negative: Includes other statements against gender equality or justifying inequalities in the welfare system.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

NB: *This category captures only statements referring to welfare-related goals, issues, or policies which are not included in the previous categories.*

Domain 3: Participation and Representation

3.1 Political representation and participation

Positive: Statements supporting political participation and political activism, gender equality in representative institutions, political parties, decision-making positions, and other public offices. May include support for gender quotas, complaints about gender under-representation.

Negative: Statements political participation and political activism, against equality or justifying gender inequalities in representative institutions, political parties, decision-making positions, and other public offices. May include criticisms against gender quotas, policy proposals fostering gender inequalities.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

3.2 Social representation and participation

Positive: Statements supporting gender equal participation in the labour market, decision-making processes in the business

sector, other non-explicitly political spheres of social life, gender equality in labour institutions, business, and other private institutions. May include support for gender quotas, complaints about gender under-representation.

Negative: Statements against or justifying gender inequalities in social participation in the labour market, decision-making processes in the business sector, labour institutions, business, and other private institutions, or other non-explicitly political spheres of social life. May include criticisms against gender quotas, policy proposals fostering gender inequalities.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

3.3 Gender-neutral language

Positive: Statements promoting the use of gender-neutral language in official communication, as well as other public spheres.

Negative: Statements against the use of gender-neutral language in official communication, as well as other public spheres.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

3.4 Gender mainstreaming

Positive: Statements promoting a policy-making approach that takes into account gender-related interests and concerns.

Negative: Statements against a policy-making approach that takes into account gender-related interests and concerns..

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

3.5 Other

Positive: Includes statements in favour of gender equality.

Negative: Includes statements against gender equality or justifying inequalities in political and social representation and participation.

Neutral: Undefined connotation.

NB: This category captures statements which refer to political or social representation/participation goals, issues, or policies which are not included in the previous categories.

Domain 4: Rights, Discrimination, and Violence

4.1 Reproductive rights and discrimination

Positive: Statements supporting access to abortion, contraception, reproductive health for (cis or trans) women, non-binary, queer, or other gender identities.

Negative: Statements curtailing or minimising issues related to access to abortion, contraception, reproductive health for (cis or trans) women, non-binary, queer, or other gender identities.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

4.2 Family rights and discrimination

Positive: Statements supporting gender equality in terms of family rights. This might include statements against gender inequalities between partners, supporting recognition of marital or family status, adoption, and other family-related policies irrespective of individuals' gender identity and/or sexual orientation.

Negative: Statements against gender equality or minimising inequalities in terms of family rights.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

4.3 Sexual and gender-based violence

Positive: Statements advocating measures and legislation aimed at curbing sexual and gender-based violence, stricter sanctions against those who commit acts of violence targeting women or LGBTBI individuals.

Negative: Statements supporting the elimination of specific safeguards for victims of gender violence, opposition to the enactment of measures and policies to prevent violence against

women or LGBTI individuals. This might include femonationalistic statements, namely statements in which violence is attribute to migrants or other minority groups.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

4.4 Immigration and citizenship

Positive: Statements advocating gender-equality in citizenship and migration policies.

Negative: Statements against, minimising or denying the need of gender-inclusive citizenship and migration policies.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

NB: *This category is not meant to capture any statement concerning citizenship or migration, but only statements in which these policies are explicitly related to gender.*

4.5 Other

Positive: Statements in favour of gender equality in terms of rights or against discrimination.

Negative: Statements minimising gender inequalities in terms of rights or openly in favour of discrimination.

Neutral: No clear connotation

NB: *This category captures other statements which are related to rights, discrimination, and violence not included in the previous categories.*

Domain 5: Gender-related notions

5.1 Feminism

Positive: General mentions in favour of feminism, feminist movements or civil society, principles, and policies.

Negative: General mentions against feminism, feminist movements or civil society, principles, and policies.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

5.2 Patriarchy and heteronormativity

Positive: Negative mentions of patriarchy and patriarchal society, or of heteronormativity.

Negative: Statements in favour of patriarchy or heteronormativity.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

5.3 LGBTQ+

Positive: General mentions in favour of LGBTQ+ and other related notions.

Negative: General mentions against LGBTQ+ and other related notions.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

5.4 Other

Positive: General mentions in favour of gender equality and other gender-related notions.

Negative: General mentions against gender equality and other gender-related notions.

Neutral: No clear connotation.

Residual category: 0

No category applies.

2.3 Coding categories: recipients, intersectionality, and policies

In addition to coding categories for goals, issues, and policies, the annotation requires the classification of further features of a quasi-sentence, namely the recipient of a statement in terms of gender and sexuality, and the intersection of the statement with other characteristics of the recipients.

2.3.1 Recipients' gender and sexuality

Although statements in manifestos might not refer to any specific recipient, in some cases they might mention it explicitly. This is informative per se, but the identification of a recipient in terms of *gender* and *sexuality* might turn useful for evaluating other aspects of a quasi-sentence (e.g., the connotation of a statement). The gender categories are split in two lists in order to capture more recipients. The list of profiles to code are the following:

Recipients' gender categories (1)

0. Undefined gender
1. Women
2. Men
3. Non-binary
4. Other

Recipients' gender categories (2)

0. Undefined
1. Cisgender
2. Transgender
3. Other

Recipients' sexuality categories

0. Undefined sexuality

1. Heterosexuals
2. Homosexuals
3. Lesbians
4. Gays
5. Queer people
6. Aro/ace
7. Other (please specify)

2.3.2 Intersectionality

Intersectionality is a theoretical perspective focusing on multiple dimensions of discrimination and the roots and effects of their 'intersections'. In our coding scheme, sexuality and gender dimensions of a statement recipient receive particular attention, and are coded separately in Step 4 (see Section 2.3.1). If the recipient's gender and/or sexuality is identified in Step 4, then in Step 5 the coder has to specify whether the argument recipient is also identified according to other (macro) characteristics.

Intersectionality categories

0. Undefined
1. Religion
2. Race and Ethnicity
3. Age
4. Class
5. Citizenship status
6. Nationality
7. Other

2.3.3 Goals, issues, and policies

This coding category aims to identify whether a quasi-sentence refers to a goal, issue or policy.

The categories are the following:

G.I.P.

0. Undefined
1. Goal: Statements referring to a desired outcome or objective that one aims to achieve;
2. Issue: Statements which refers to a matter or a problem that needs to be addressed or resolved, which causes difficulty, concern, or challenge;
3. Policy: specific course of action or a set of principles or guidelines to direct decisions and actions.

2.3.4 Policy categories

We distinguish between two main categories of policies, relief/resource-based ones, and regulations. The specific meaning of these categories and the codes are the following:

Policy type

0. Undefined
1. Relief/Resources: Solutions concerned with treating the symptoms of gender-based needs through the provision of resources but also services;
2. Regulation: Rules which change rights, duties, or procedures. This might include legal protection/anti-discrimination laws, family rights/duties, gender quotas;
3. Other: Policies not included in the previous steps.

2.4 Expert survey

When completed the classification of a manifesto's quasi-sentences the coder should then fill in a survey dedicated to a manifesto as a whole. These surveys are used to provide further information about the document, in particular features which cannot be directly evaluated at the quasi-sentence level or only via aggregation. It is important to note that such survey should be filled *only* considering the content of the manifesto. The coder, then, should avoid to fill the survey considering its own evaluations of the party.

2.4.1 Expert survey main dimensions

All the following items except the first one are quasi-interval measures, namely ordinal items with 11 answer categories (0-10).

Gender ontology

Question: Which is the gender ontology employed in the manifesto?

Categories:

- **Essentialist**: gender and sex are the same and inseparable;
- **Constructivist**: biological sex is mediated through social construction of femininity and masculinity;
- **Other**.

Residual category: Don't know (99)

Gender Binary

Question: To what extent the manifesto promotes a binary conception of gender?

Poles: Non-binary (0) – Binary (10)

Residual category: Don't know (99)

Feminism

Question: To what extent the manifesto promotes women's rights on the basis of the equality of the sexes?

Poles: Anti-feminist (0) – Feminist (10)

Residual category: Don't know (99)

Patriarchy

Question: To what extent the manifesto promotes a social system in which positions of dominance and privilege are primarily held by men?

Poles: Non-patriarchal (0) – Patriarchal (10)

Residual category: Don't know (99)

Heteronormativity

Question: To what extent the manifesto interlinks gender with sexuality resulting in a normative system of prescribed heterosexuality?

Poles: Non-heteronormative (0) – Heteronormative (10)

Residual category: Don't know (99)

3. Data codebook

The coding of the manifestos' quasi-sentences based on the MGA codebook was performed between December 2023 and April 2024. The data provided by our 11 coders were harmonised and pooled in a single data frame which consists in the data basis of our analyses.

To date, the number of electoral programmes analysed is 412. The total number of quasi-sentences is 446,625 and the number of *qs* of each manifesto oscillates between a minimum of 19 to a maximum of 9,197 *qs* (Mean= 1,084; Median = 671; Standard deviation = 1,167). Of these, 18,887 *qs* (4.23% of the total) have been coded as gender-related, with huge differences across the context of interest. Indeed, the number of sentences, without considering temporal variations, oscillates between a minimum of 57 (0.83% of the country total, 0.01% of the total) in the Danish EP elections' manifestos, and a maximum of 9,971 (7.17% of the country total, 2.23% of the total) for the Spanish national elections' manifestos.

In addition to data concerning coded quasi-sentences the MGA procedure developed by WP4 includes the completion of an expert survey aiming at gauging broader gender-related concepts which might be detected only after reading the full text of party manifestos. Overall, coders have been able to code most of the documents (313, 76% of the available manifestos) at least on one of the relevant dimensions.

3.1 Manifesto verbatim data codebook

Variable	Dataset indicator
Manifesto project (EM or MARPOR)	project
Country	country
Election date	edate
Party code (as in the original manifesto project)	party_code
Party name (original language)	party_name_or
Party name (English translation)	party_name_en
Position of the quasi-sentence in the manifesto	pos
Quasi-sentence	qsentence
Connotation (i.e., sentiment)	connotation
Recipients' gender (1)	rgender_1
Recipients' gender (2)	rgender_2
Recipients' sexuality	rsexuality
Intersectionality	intersect
Goal, issue, or policy	gip
Policy type	policy_type

3.2 Survey data codebook

Variable	Dataset indicator
Manifesto project (EM or MARPOR)	project
Country	country
Election date	edate

Party code (as in the original manifesto project)	party_code
Party name (original language)	party_name_or
Party name (English translation)	party_name_en
Gender ontology	ontology
Gender binary	binary
Feminism	feminism
Patriarchy	patriarchy
Heteronormativity	hnormativity